

A Study On Factors Influencing Brand Preferences Among Baby Boomers And Generation Y Buyers In Passenger Car Segment Focussing Chennai Region

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INTRODUCTION :

Transportation system is a prodigy by human kind which satisfies the most essential feature called mobility. India is one of the most encouraging and deliberately growing economies followed by china as it has enormous consumer base populations having an ample amount of spending space [source: Auto-facts 2016 Q3 forecast release]. It creates employments for thousands and spawn many entrepreneurs. Giant number of foreign brands have come and established in to the Indian automobile industry but due to the constant change in consumer preferences not all of them were able to drive the success waves. It is so convoluted because of the divergent regions, culture and income levels of the people. Therefore in order to attract the customers the marketer has to understand their customers well and also the local market conditions to sustain in their minds.

The Indian luxury car market witnessed growth in 2015 and the three German players Mercedes Benz, Audi and BMW dominated the market, posting combined sales of approximately 31,000 units. In 2015, the Indian luxury car market sold 35,300 units and it is expected that sales will grow to 87,300 units by 2020. The sector is expected to grow at a rate of 15% per annum in the period 2015-2018. Growth in the sector has been boosted by a number of new product launches across price points coupled with enhanced dealer network beyond the metropolitan areas in India. Other growth drivers include availability of robust financing options and a focus on localisation of parts. The luxury automobile manufacturers are consistently targeting the young achievers in India who are emerging as an important target segment for the luxury segment in the country. Product launches are catering to the demand from this segment.[Source: "Indian Luxury Car Market: Sector Study 2016"].

According to the news reported in Times of India by Nandini Sen Gupta on May 6 , 2015 chennai tops in

vehicle density.Chennai tops the list with 2093 followed by Pune with 1260, Mumbai with 1014, Hyderabad with 723, Kolkata with 355 and Delhi with 245. The reason for this is Delhi's enormous advantage in road length. Compared to 1800 km in Chennai and Pune, 2000 km in Mumbai and a mere 1400 km in Kolkata, Delhi boasts around 30,000 km of road length. This is one of the major reasons for me having chosen chennai as my specific area of research.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Marketing strategies are often designed to influence consumer behaviour and lead to profitable exchanges. Every single element of the marketing mix can affect and influence the consumers in different ways (Peter and Donnelly, 2004). The choice method of consumers is impacted by individual and environmental

influences. Motives, values, personality and lifestyle represents individual characteristics and culture, family and reference teams represents social influences.

Situational influences, like a consumer's money condition, additionally influence the consumption choice method. The positioning decision is central to the success of a brand (Pham and Muthukrishnan, 2002; and Punj and Moon, 2002) as it directly shapes customers' perceptions and brand choice decisions (Aaker and Shansby, 1982; and Carpenter, Glazer, and Nakamoto, 1994).

Human resources expert Heathfield (2015) defined Baby Boomers (Boomers) as the generation of people born in a baby boom following World War II, 1946-1964. Boomers have had good health, constitute the wealthiest generation, and optimistically view the world as improving over time. Today, the oldest Boomers are considering their retirement options and are seeking ways and opportunities to make their elder years personally meaningful.

Generation Y is also referred to as Gen Y, Echo Boomers, Millennials or Millennials, Internet Generation, Connect 24/7, and Leave No One Behind (Schroer, 2015) are Born in 1981-1995s. They are the first to grow up with computers and the Internet as a significant part of their lives. Constant experience in the networked world has had a profound impact on their style in approaching problem-solving situations. This generation of worker is coming into the workforce with networking, multiprocessing, and global-minded skills that the traditionalists and baby boomers could not have imagined.

M. Akber and P. Ashok Kumar (2012), in the study of consumer buying behaviour, has proved that many factors like price, income, distribution of income, competition with alternatives, utility, consumer preference (economic factors) and factors like culture, attitude, social values, lifestyles, personality, size of family, education, health standards etc., play a major role in buying behaviour of customers.

Internet in India is accessed by just one in seventeen people, but the research as shown that every third car buyer in the country's top cities start their search on the world-wide web. As per Sharma (2010), four out of every ten new car buyers and three in every ten used car buyers, use internet to do initial research, before making the purchase.

Hence, an understanding of the consumer behaviour enables a marketer to understand and take decisions which are compatible to consumer needs. This study classifies 3 major determinants of factors influencing brand preferences namely overall environmental stimuli, marketing stimuli and other stimuli on baby boomers and generation Y. Based on these factors the marketers can understand the generational differences by knowing the gaps, similarities and differences between them, their tastes and preferences towards Indian and foreign brands and help them to cater their needs successfully.

OBJECTIVES:

- To analyse the factors influencing brand preferences among baby boomers and generation Y.

RESEARCH DESIGN :

The research design is exploratory in nature. The sample consists of baby boomers and generation Y buyers staying in Chennai city meeting qualifications such as well educated, well informed of latest trends & currently using a car. Convenient sampling technique is applied in this research paper. The sample size is 401 buyers living in Chennai and meeting the above mentioned criteria. The structured questionnaire was used to collect the primary data.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

1. Frequency Distribution of Generational cohorts among buyers

Generational cohorts	Frequency	Percent
Generation Y	208	51.871
Baby Boomers	193	48.129
Total	401	100.0

51.87% of total sample of car buyers are from Generation Y category, 48.129% of buyers are from baby boomers category.

2. Frequency Distribution of annual family income among generational cohorts

Generational cohorts	Annual Family Income in lakhs			Total
	Below 7	7-15	Above 15	
Generation Y	63 (30.3%) [32.6%]	109 (52.4%) [30.2%]	36 (17.3%) [16.1%]	208 (100.0%) [26.7%]
Baby Boomers	58 (30.1%) [30.1%]	92 (47.7%) [25.5%]	43 (22.3%) [19.2%]	193 (100.0%) [24.8%]

Note: 1. The value within () refers to Row Percentage

2. The value within [] refers to Column Percentage

Based on the row percentage, maximum 52.4% of generation Y category respondents fall under annual family income of 7 to 15 lakhs and minimum 17.3% belong to above 15 lakh category. Likewise maximum 47.7% of baby boomers category respondents fall under annual family income of 7 to 15 lakhs and minimum 22.3% belong to above 15 lakh category.

Generational cohorts	Role in the car purchase				Total
	Only decision maker	Decision makers and played decisive role	Decision makers, but not played decisive role	Totally decided by others	
Generation Y	35 (16.8%) [20.2%]	119 (57.2%) [31.2%]	51 (24.5%) [25.9%]	3 (1.4%) [11.5%]	208 (100.0%) [26.7%]
Baby Boomers	36 (18.7%) [20.8%]	98 (50.8%) [25.7%]	47 (24.4%) [23.9%]	12 (6.2%) [46.2%]	193 (100.0%) [24.8%]

3. Frequency Distribution of role played in car purchase among generational cohorts
Note: 1. The value within () refers to Row Percentage

2. The value within [] refers to Column Percentage

Based on the row percentage, a majority share of 57.2% in generation Y respondents is one of the decision makers and played a decisive role in purchasing the car and a very minimal percentage of 1.4% have purchased a car which is totally decided by others. Furthermore the maximum percentage of baby boomers (50.8%) have been one of the decision maker and played a decisive role in purchasing the car.

4. Frequency Distribution of brand of car purchased among generational cohorts

Generational cohorts	Brand of car purchased		Total
	Indian	Foreign	
Generation Y	49 (23.6%) [23.9%]	159 (76.4%) [27.7%]	208 (100.0%) [26.7%]
Baby Boomers	58 (30.1%) [28.3%]	135 (69.9%) [23.6%]	193 (100.0%) [24.8%]

Note: 1. The value within () refers to Row Percentage

2. The value within [] refers to Column Percentage

Based on the row percentage, 23.6% of Indian brand cars and 76.4% of foreign brand cars have been purchased by generation Y. Likewise 30.1% of Indian brand cars and 69.9% of foreign brand cars have been purchased by baby boomers .

5. Frequency Distribution of brand preference among generational cohorts

Generational cohorts	Brand preference		Total
	Indian brands	Foreign brands	
Generation Y	72 (34.6%) [18.6%]	136 (65.4%) [34.8%]	208 (100.0%) [26.7%]
Baby Boomers	79 (40.9%) [20.4%]	114 (59.1%) [29.2%]	193 (100.0%) [24.8%]

Note: 1. The value within () refers to Row Percentage

2. The value within [] refers to Column Percentage

Based on the row percentage, majority share of 65.4% in generation Y prefers foreign brands in general likewise baby boomers with 59.1% also prefer the same.

HYPOTHESIS 1

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between brand of car purchased with respect to dimension of brand preference among generation Y buyers

Table 1 - t test for significant difference between brand of car purchased with respect to dimension of brand preference among generation Y buyers

Overall factors influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers	Brand of car purchased				t value	P value
	Indian		Foreign			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Cultural	26.16	3.13	24.80	4.10	2.142	0.033*
Social	17.67	1.81	17.46	2.44	0.568	0.571
Personal	26.12	2.40	25.60	3.11	1.086	0.279
Psychological	30.80	2.37	30.14	3.28	1.288	0.199
Economical	27.29	2.02	25.91	2.89	3.112	0.002**
Overall Environmental Stimuli	128.04	8.65	123.91	12.34	2.185	0.030*
Product Referent	50.18	2.96	48.61	5.19	2.022	0.044*
Task Referent	31.86	1.47	30.74	2.85	2.645	0.009**
User Referent	26.51	1.89	25.58	2.78	2.189	0.030*
Product	108.55	4.75	104.92	9.47	2.580	0.011*
Price	22.65	1.36	21.82	2.16	2.552	0.011*
Place	22.47	1.24	21.75	2.27	2.109	0.036*
Promotion	26.57	1.58	25.78	2.95	1.801	0.073
Overall Marketing Stimuli	180.24	6.19	174.28	14.82	2.743	0.007**
Digital Media	27.49	1.49	27.04	2.74	1.089	0.277
Customer Relationship Management	68.47	3.70	66.42	6.44	2.119	0.035*
Celebrity Endorsement	17.00	2.40	16.74	3.09	0.536	0.592
Country of Origin	16.27	2.75	14.88	3.01	2.870	0.005**
Green marketing	22.63	2.26	21.57	3.40	2.045	0.042*
Overall Other Stimuli	151.86	9.01	146.66	14.60	2.355	0.019*

- Note : 1. ** denotes significant at 1% level
 2. * denotes significant at 5% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level with regard to dimension of economical, task referent, overall marketing stimuli, country of origin. Hence there is significance difference between brand of car purchased with regard to the dimension of above factors influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers.

Since P value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis rejected at 5% level, with regard to cultural, overall environmental stimuli, product referent, user referent, product, price, place, customer relationship management, green marketing, overall other stimuli, ownership cost. Hence there is significance difference

between brand of car purchased with regard to the dimension of above factors influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers.

There is no significance difference between brand of car purchased with regard to social, personal, psychological, promotion, digital media, celebrity endorsement, purchase service quality, engine performance, comfort and functionality, safety, quality, brand image, brand satisfaction cum loyalty and overall satisfaction on purchase decision. Hence the null hypothesis accepted with regard to above factors.

HYPOTHESIS 2

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between brand of car preferred in general with respect to dimension of factors influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers

Table 2 - t test for significant difference between brand of car preferred in general with respect to dimension of factors influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers

Overall factors influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers	Brand of car preferred				t value	P value
	Indian brands		Global brands			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Cultural	26.15	3.43	24.57	4.08	2.801	0.006**
Social	17.49	1.80	17.52	2.54	0.107	0.915
Personal	25.78	3.19	25.69	2.84	0.200	0.841
Psychological	30.44	3.03	30.22	3.14	0.495	0.621
Economical	26.81	2.59	25.93	2.82	2.197	0.029*
Overall Environmental Stimuli	126.67	11.84	123.93	11.54	1.610	0.109
Product Referent	48.82	4.18	49.07	5.11	0.352	0.725
Task Referent	30.96	2.56	31.02	2.68	0.166	0.869
User Referent	26.44	2.14	25.46	2.80	2.617	0.010**
Total Product	106.22	7.86	105.54	9.16	0.533	0.595
Price	22.32	1.70	21.85	2.17	1.583	0.115
Place	21.97	1.82	21.90	2.23	0.246	0.806
Promotion	26.25	2.01	25.82	3.01	1.101	0.272
Overall Marketing Stimuli	176.76	11.57	175.11	14.46	0.838	0.403
Digital Media	27.17	1.85	27.14	2.80	0.074	0.941
Customer Relationship Management	66.83	5.10	66.94	6.39	0.124	0.902
Celebrity Endorsement	17.00	2.12	16.70	3.29	0.703	0.483
Country of Origin	16.33	2.40	14.61	3.13	4.081	<0.001**
Green marketing	22.65	2.23	21.38	3.54	2.770	0.006**
Overall Other Stimuli	149.99	10.17	146.77	15.09	1.622	0.106

Note : 1. ** denotes significant at 1% level

2. * denotes significant at 5% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level with regard to dimension of cultural, user referent, country of origin, green marketing. Hence there is significance difference between brand of car preferred in general with regard to the dimension of above factors influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers.

Since P value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis rejected at 5% level, with regard to economical factor. Hence there is significance difference between brand of car purchased with regard to the dimension of economical factor influencing brand preference among generation Y buyers

There is no significance difference between brand of car preferred in general with regard to social, personal, psychological, overall environmental stimuli, product referent, task referent, total product, price, place, promotion, overall marketing stimuli, purchase service quality, engine performance, comfort and functionality, safety, quality, brand image, ownership cost, brand satisfaction cum loyalty and overall satisfaction in purchase decision. Hence the null hypothesis accepted with regard to above factors.

HYPOTHESIS 3

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between brand of car purchased with respect to dimension of factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers

Table 3 - t test for significant difference between brand of car purchased with respect to factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers

Overall factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers	Brand of car purchased				t value	P value
	Indian		Foreign			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Cultural	20.52	5.89	21.87	5.64	1.511	0.132
Social	15.40	3.05	16.53	2.46	2.728	0.007**
Personal	22.29	4.48	24.15	4.06	2.821	0.005**
Psychological	29.00	4.28	29.58	3.11	1.052	0.294
Economical	26.40	4.01	25.23	3.64	1.980	0.049*
Overall Environmental Stimuli	113.60	13.44	117.36	12.13	1.910	0.058
Product Referent	44.03	5.43	46.05	5.58	2.321	0.021*
Task Referent	31.21	3.54	31.65	3.14	0.868	0.387
User Referent	26.91	3.02	27.74	2.31	2.070	0.040*
Total Product	102.16	7.18	105.44	6.73	3.052	0.003**
Price	22.72	2.50	22.44	2.50	0.712	0.477
Place	20.60	2.81	20.56	2.47	0.100	0.920
Promotion	27.00	3.30	26.50	4.02	0.828	0.409
Overall Marketing Stimuli	172.48	11.24	174.96	10.19	1.498	0.136
Digital Media	18.66	8.20	20.17	7.43	1.259	0.210
Customer Relationship Management	66.79	4.64	66.99	5.37	0.246	0.806
Celebrity Endorsement	11.41	5.22	12.34	5.25	1.126	0.261
Country of Origin	12.10	5.36	12.96	5.41	1.015	0.311
Green marketing	17.31	4.50	18.55	4.64	1.714	0.088
Overall Other Stimuli	126.28	19.33	131.01	18.98	1.582	0.115

- Note : 1. ** denotes significant at 1% level
 2. * denotes significant at 5% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level with regard to dimension of social, personal and total product. Hence there is significance difference between brand of car purchased with regard to the dimension of above factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers.

Since P value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis rejected at 5% level, with regard to economical, product referent, user referent, comfort and functionality and brand image. Hence there is significance difference between brand of car purchased with regard to the dimension of above factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers.

There is no significance difference between brand of car purchased with regard to cultural, psychological, overall environmental stimuli, task referent, price, place, promotion, overall marketing stimuli, digital media, customer relationship management, country of origin, green marketing, overall other stimuli, purchase service quality, engine performance, safety, quality, ownership cost and overall satisfaction on purchase decision. Hence the null hypothesis accepted with regard to above factors.

HYPOTHESIS 4

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between brand of car preferred with respect to dimension of factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers

Table 4 - t test for significant difference between brand of car preferred with respect to dimension of factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers

Overall factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers	Brand of car prefer in general				t value	P value
	Indian brands		Global brands			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Cultural	20.03	5.75	22.46	5.53	2.963	0.003**
Social	15.57	2.72	16.62	2.61	2.710	0.007**
Personal	22.32	4.55	24.47	3.83	3.560	<0.001**
Psychological	29.46	4.27	29.37	2.86	0.170	0.865
Economical	26.48	3.03	24.96	4.13	2.803	0.006**
Overall Environmental Stimuli	113.85	13.19	117.89	12.00	2.207	0.028*
Product Referent	44.66	5.37	45.99	5.71	1.633	0.104
Task Referent	31.51	3.48	31.53	3.12	0.042	0.967
User Referent	27.27	2.74	27.65	2.43	1.020	0.309
Total Product	103.43	7.26	105.17	6.78	1.700	0.091
Price	22.62	2.72	22.46	2.34	0.424	0.672
Place	20.18	2.82	20.85	2.35	1.803	0.073
Promotion	27.01	3.24	26.40	4.16	1.091	0.276
Overall Marketing Stimuli	173.24	11.96	174.89	9.44	1.066	0.288
Digital Media	18.06	7.75	20.86	7.45	2.523	0.012*
Customer Relationship Management	66.94	5.81	66.93	4.67	0.009	0.993
Celebrity Endorsement	11.38	5.33	12.54	5.16	1.510	0.133
Country of Origin	11.82	5.46	13.32	5.28	1.904	0.058
Green marketing	17.54	4.40	18.61	4.74	1.587	0.114
Overall Other Stimuli	125.75	19.19	132.25	18.76	2.347	0.020*

Note : 1. ** denotes significant at 1% level

2. * denotes significant at 5% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level with regard to dimension of cultural, social, personal, economical, brand satisfaction and loyalty. Hence there is significance difference between brand of car preferred with regard to the dimension of above factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers.

Since P value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis rejected at 5% level, with regard to overall environmental stimuli, digital media, overall other stimuli, comfort and functionality. Hence there is significance difference between brand of car preferred with regard to the dimension of above factors influencing brand preference among baby boomers.

There is no significance difference between brand of car preferred with regard to psychological, product referent, task referent, user referent, total product, price, place, promotion, overall marketing stimuli, customer relationship management, celebrity endorsement, country of origin, green marketing, purchase service quality, engine performance, safety, quality, brand image, ownership cost and overall satisfaction on purchase decision. Hence the null hypothesis accepted with regard to above factors.

Hypothesis 5

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing environmental stimuli among generation Y buyers

Table 5 Friedman test for significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing environmental stimuli among generation Y buyers

Factors influencing environmental stimuli among generation Y buyers	Mean Rank	Chi-Square value	P value
Cultural	2.64	26.753	<0.001 **
Social	3.33		
Personal	2.83		
Psychological	3.04		
Economical	3.16		

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 percent level of significance. Hence concluded that there is significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing environmental stimuli among generation Y buyers. Based on mean rank social factor (3.33) is most Effective of environmental stimuli among generation Y buyers, followed by economical factor (3.16), psychological (3.04), personal (2.83) and Cultural (2.64).

Hypothesis 6

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing marketing stimuli among generation Y buyers

Table 6 Friedman test for significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing marketing stimuli among generation Y buyers.

Factors influencing marketing stimuli among generation Y buyers	Me an Rank	Chi-Squ are valu e	P value
Product	2.44	3.870	0.276
Price	2.57		
Place	2.59		
Promotion	2.39		

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence it is concluded that there is no significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing marketing stimuli among generation Y buyers.

Hypothesis 7

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing other stimuli among generation Y buyers

Table 7 Friedman test for significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing other stimuli among generation Y buyers

Factors influencing other stimuli among generation Y buyers	M ea n Rank	Chi-Squ are valu e	P value
Digital Media	3.74	201.332	<0.001 **
Customer Relationship Management	3.33		
Celebrity Endorsement	2.89		
Country of Origin	1.78		
Green marketing	3.26		

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 percent level of significance. Hence concluded that there is significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing other stimuli among generation Y buyers. Based on mean rank digital media (3.74) is most Effective of other stimuli among generation Y buyers, followed by customer relationship management (3.33), green marketing (3.26), celebrity endorsement (2.89) and country of origin (1.78).

Hypothesis 8

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing environmental stimuli among baby boomers.

Table 8 Friedman test for significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing environmental stimuli among baby boomers.

Factors influencing environmental stimuli among baby boomers	Mean Rank	Chi-Square value	P value
Cultural	2.27	74.194	<0.001 **
Social	3.19		
Personal	2.78		
Psychological	3.33		
Economical	3.43		

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 percent level of significance. Hence concluded that there is significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing environmental stimuli among baby boomers. Based on mean rank economical factor (3.43) is most Effective of environmental stimuli among baby boomers, followed by psychological factor (3.33), social (3.19), personal (2.78) and Cultural (2.27).

Hypothesis 9

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing marketing stimuli among baby boomers.

Table 9 - Friedman test for significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing marketing stimuli among baby boomers.

Factors influencing marketing stimuli among baby boomers	Mean Rank	Chi-Square value	P value
Product	2.43	73.213	<0.001 **
Price	2.88		
Place	1.91		
Promotion	2.78		

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 percent level of significance. Hence concluded that there is significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing marketing stimuli among baby boomers. Based on mean rank price (2.88) is most Effective of marketing stimuli among baby boomers, followed by promotion (2.78), product (2.43) and place (1.91).

Hypothesis 10

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing other stimuli among baby boomers.

Table 10 - Friedman test for significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing other stimuli among baby boomers.

Factors influencing other stimuli among baby boomers	Mean Rank	Chi-Square value	P value
Digital Media	2.74	166.261	<0.001 **
Customer Relationship Management	4.11		
Celebrity Endorsement	2.40		
Country of Origin	2.45		
Green marketing	3.31		

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 percent level of significance. Hence concluded that there is significant difference among mean ranks towards factors influencing other stimuli among baby boomers. Based on mean customer relationship management (4.11) is most Effective of other stimuli among baby boomers, is followed by green marketing (3.31), digital media (2.74) , country of origin (2.45) and celebrity endorsement (2.40).

FINDINGS:

- Out of the total respondents 51.87% of buyers are from Generation Y category and the remaining are from baby boomers.
- The maximum number of generation Y and baby boomer respondents annual family income falls under the range of 7 to 15 lakhs category.
- A majority share of 57.2% in generation Y and 50.8% in baby boomers are one of the decision maker and played a decisive role in purchasing the car
- Both the generations have purchased more of foreign brand cars than Indian brands because the variety of foreign brand cars available in India are much higher than Indian brands.
- Generation Y and baby boomers prefer foreign brands over Indian brands.
- t test findings indicate that there is a greater influence of economical, task referent, overall marketing stimuli and country of origin factors influencing brand of car purchased by generation Y buyers whereas in case of a baby boomers social factor, personal and total product have a greater influence in brand of car purchased.
- Social, personal, economical, brand satisfaction and loyalty largely influence baby boomers in their preference of cars whereas user referent, country of origin, green marketing influence generation y preference of cars. cultural factor commonly influence both the generation.
- Based on mean rank social factor (3.33) is most Effective of environmental stimuli among generation Y buyers, followed by economical factor, psychological, personal and Cultural.
- Economical factor (3.43) is most Effective of environmental stimuli among baby boomers, followed by psychological factor (3.33), social (3.19), personal (2.78) and Cultural (2.27).
- Based on mean rank price (2.88) is most Effective of marketing stimuli among baby boomers, followed by promotion (2.78), product (2.43) and place (1.91).
- Digital media (3.74) is most Effective of other stimuli among generation Y buyers, followed by customer relationship management (3.33), green marketing (3.26), celebrity endorsement (2.89) and country of origin (1.78).

- Customer relationship management (4.11) is most Effective of other stimuli among baby boomers, is followed by green marketing (3.31), digital media (2.74) , country of origin (2.45) and celebrity endorsement (2.40).

CONCLUSION:

Based on the above findings , the study suggests that marketer should analyse the target audience by understanding their tastes, preference, beliefs and wants. Marketers should recognise that a success mantra of developing a marketing strategy primely depends on “knowing your customers”. Moreover, the effectiveness not only dependent on the marketing stimuli but consumer buying behaviour and composition of target market also play vital role. In order to develop a best suitable strategy, marketers should understand all those stimuli which affect car purchase behaviour and brand choice process of the buyers. Furthermore buyers can never be generalised, the study proves that there is a dissidence between generations in their perceptions and wants. A best integrated marketing strategy can be made for different generations according to their tastes and preferences and this in-depth marketing strategy will attract more number of buyers in the future. The findings show that generation Y are more attracted towards information in digital media plat forms and on the other hand baby boomers most impactful feature is customer relationship management. Green marketing is the new trend among buyers and the awareness about it is alarming day by day. Price is most influential factor among baby boomers and the youth have less priority towards it because it has become almost standard among all the dealers. Social factors such as ‘status’ , family and friends reviews are considered more important to generation Y whereas economic factors such as ‘easy availability financial loans’, value for money are the factors that drive baby boomers. Thus each generation so different from another so integrated marketing strategy focussing each generation is the key to success. In line with a very famous quote “the aim of marketing is to know and understand the customer so well, the product or service fits him and sell itself “ — Peter Drucker

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